

Jute Tower

Experience in Natural Fibre Coreless Winding Fabrication with Collaborative Robot

Rakhmat Fitranto Aditra¹, Galuh Kresnadian Tedjawanata², and
Andry Widyowijatnoko³

^{1,2,3}*School of Architecture, Planning and Policy Development, Institut
Teknologi Bandung, Jl. Ganesa 10, West Java, Indonesia.*

¹*rakhmat@itb.ac.id, ORCID: 0000-0002-4886-7418*

²*galuhkresnadiant@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0003-3908-9164*

³*andry@itb.ac.id, ORCID: 0000-0002-0597-4600*

Abstract. The ATRIA Exhibition 2024 at the Bandung Institute of Technology necessitated an installation as a centrepiece. The centrepiece must be highly biodegradable to minimise storage needs post-exhibition. Jute Tower was developed and created utilising robotic fibre winding and manual fabrication with natural materials: jute fibre and bone glue. The chosen design for the Jute Tower is essentially an inverted truncated pyramid, with 40 distinct jute fibre panels supported by four sets of 6-mm steel bar frames. The construction of the Jute Tower serves as an excellent application of digital fabrication, particularly in robotic fibre winding. The utilisation of natural fibres and adhesives demonstrates benefits for collaborative human-robot interaction. The integration of manual fabrication and human interaction facilitates the learning curve associated with robotic fabrication. Nevertheless, it also introduces imperfections and inaccuracies, which remain permissible for the installation's objectives. The installation of Jute Tower has demonstrated that natural fibre infused with natural resin can serve as an alternative biodegradable material for exhibitions, replacing the predominantly oil-based adhesive timber panels utilised in Indonesia. The utilisation of bone glue facilitates reduced volume during disposal, while it necessitates additional logistics.

Keywords. Coreless fibre winding, collaborative robot, natural fibre, disposability.

1. Introduction

1.1. BACKGROUND: EXHIBITION WASTE

The environmental impact of exhibitions has become a growing concern in recent years, as the industry continues to generate significant amounts of waste. While the

waste produced by exhibitions can take various forms, including paper, plastic, and food waste, the scale of the problem is significant, with some exhibitions generating as much as 12,000 tons of garbage (Ding et al., 2019).

Recently, creative industries have focused more on natural fibres. The textile and fashion sectors have investigated using jute, ramie, and roselle to make more sustainable products (Hamdan et al., 2020). In mechanical properties, natural fibre composites were shown to be stronger, lighter, and biodegradable than standard reinforcements (Elanchezhian et al., 2018).

Another natural material that could be used is natural fibre. ITKE University of Stuttgart has shown the possibility of using natural fibre for coreless winding construction (Gil Pérez, Guo, & Knippers, 2022). Compared to timber components that mainly involve cutting and subtracting, coreless winding construction theoretically does not generate fibre waste and useless material. However, examples of coreless winding construction are all robotically wound.

The Bandung Institute of Technology architecture program were having annual exhibitions. Installation requires fresh materials, even though most of the panel employs stored reusable panels. Unique components make installations hard to reuse.

1.2. COLLABORATIVE ROBOTIC FABRICATION

Robotic fabrication is beneficial for precise fabrication. This advantage is more critical for natural fibre coreless winding due to its sensitive characteristics. Coreless fibre winding has multiple fabrication parameters that need to be maintained to have precise structural performance. Examples include winding tension, resin viscosity, and winding speed. (Gil Pérez et al., 2022). Natural fibre has even more parameters affecting its structural performance than carbon fibre.

However, robotic fabrication is a new approach in architecture (Melenbrink, Werfel, & Menges, 2020). Unlike digital manufacturing, which uses existing machinery, robotic fabrication, especially coreless winding, requires additional setup and tools. Indonesian architects rarely use these setups and technologies. Manufacturing with robots also improves efficiency and precision. Robotic manufacturing accuracy and uniformity complement humans' inventive design and monitoring. Robots can manage thread tension, glue viscosity, and winding speed while manufacturing with natural fibres. Robotics boost productivity and reduce quality-lowering errors (Bogue, 2018).

At Bandung Institute of Technology's architecture program, Universal Robots' UR10 can work with humans. Our robotics skills and logistics are limited, but we have expertise with computationally enhanced yet manually assembled show installations (Aditra & Widyowijatnoko, 2016; A. Widyowijatnoko, Irwanuddin, & Aditra, 2019; Andry Widyowijatnoko, Aditra, & Cungwin, 2021). As our institution starts to introduce computational design and digital fabrication for architecture, the collaborative 6-axis robotic arm is one of the most advanced robots employed.

Natural fibres, coreless winding, and collaborative robotic fabrication were used to build the Jute Tower for the annual ATRIA exhibition at Bandung Institute of Technology on September 9, 2024. This paper describes Jute Tower design and production and evaluates fibre panel disposability.

Figure 1. Fibre panel on the moulding panel (left) and the detached fibre panel with dowels intact (right)

2. Design

Its construction system deeply influenced the Jute Tower's design. Due to the robot arm's limited reach, panels would form the tower's skin. In previous fibre winding, steel bolts were used as anchors. Removal of bolts was difficult as the panels dried. Thus, wooden dowels were anchors (Figure 1 left). Apart from being cheaper than steel bolts, hardwood dowels stayed with the panels, unattached from the moulding (Figure 1 right). The fibres and wooden dowels can be discarded after the exhibition without separating it. The dowels adhere to moulding panels by friction. Manufacturing friction shouldn't be excessively loose or tight. Figure 1 left shows 2-cm medium-density fibreboard moulding panels. The thickness should provide appropriate friction and torque resistance for the placed anchor.

Fibre panels were manufactured with bone glue and 4 mm jute rope. Although weaker than synthetic or metal fibres, jute fibres are biodegradable and eco-friendly. Jute rope was used because of market availability. Other than being natural, bone glue was chosen for safety and solubility. Hot water dissolves bone glue after disassembling.

The installation is meant to be the exhibition's centrepiece. Since the display is for the public, size and tall proportion are better than intricate geometry, which also requires complex mould. Thus, a 3-meter inverted truncated pyramid was chosen (Figure 2). The four faces have 10 panels in 5 vertical levels each. Based on earlier fibre winding work, these panels were projected to be too weak for that height. Thus, four 6-mm steel bar frames formed this installation's skeleton. As exhibition specialists, the contractors reused these steel bar frames.

A single goal of winding pattern design is to reduce moulding panel count. Each fibre panels only resists their own weight. There's no aesthetic or visual goal for the winding design either. Figure 2 shows that panel bases lengthen with panel level. The panel's trapezoid height is all same.

The moulding panel design addresses this association. Only two rows of 16 holes at the trapezoid bases make up the moulding panels. Which dowel holes are utilized depends on panel level (Figure 2). The level 1 panel uses only 10 and 11 dowel holes for the shorter and longer base, respectively. The level 5 panel uses all dowel holes except one on the shorter trapezoid base. Level 1 panels have 10 dowels and 60 cm shorter bases. The installation slope depends on this dimension and the trapezoid's steadily increasing base (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Design of Jute Tower

The winding pattern is back and forth between the top and bottom rows of dowels. The order of the winding in each row is primarily random, which is mainly for aesthetic purposes. One other parameter that decides the winding pattern is the grouping of the dowels. (Figure 3a-b). The purpose of grouping the dowels is also mainly aesthetic. This grouping also resulted in less bulky and more distributed panel.

Evaluating the winding pattern to avoid certain patterns was done manually. The only avoided winding pattern is if the order of winding between the top and bottom row is reversed, making all the spanned rope intersect in the middle. It can lead to a bulking centre, possibly touching the MDF panel and making it difficult to detach (Figure 3c). All panels are unique, generated by changing the divisions and random seed value.

Each panel consists of 2 cladding layers and four frame layers stacked at different levels. The order of the layers from the bottom is frame, first cladding, 2 consecutive frames, second cladding, and lastly, the last frame. The purpose of this stacking design is to give some thickness to the panel.

Figure 3. Fibre panel syntax example: (a) randomized - 1 group, (b) randomized - 3 group, and (c) reversed order

Figure 4. End effector (left), delamination of the first end effector (right), and examples of syringe nozzle (right)

3. Fabrication

3.1. END EFFECTOR

The end effector is a large syringe connected to the robotic arm with a 3D-printed part. The fibre passes through the syringe that is already filled with bone glue (Figure 4 left). The syringe remained loosely held to allow for rotation. The purpose of the wing parts is to tie a rubber band, which will prevent the syringe from moving upwards when the fibre is tensioned.

There are some adjustments made throughout the fabrication process. First, the 3D printed parts were reprinted because of the first 3D printed parts delamination (Figure 4 middle). Thus, the second 3D printed part has its layering direction flipped. The nozzle of the syringe was amended several times. Without any additional part, the fibres came out of the nozzle in a very tight angle and the syringe nozzle scraped the glue at the top of the fibre. Thus, an additional 3D-printed nozzle was added to the syringe nozzle. This 3D-printed nozzle was designed to be detachable. Thus, it should be able to clamp the nozzle with the help of a zip tie. However, this 3D-printed nozzle went through several amend and remaking because it tends to split at the tip, which significantly reduces its effectiveness (Figure 4 right).

3.2. WINDING PATH

The winding path algorithm converts the panel winding pattern to the winding path of the Tool Centre Point (TCP). The main aim of the algorithm is to avoid collision with the dowel and fibres. To avoid dowels, the winding path circles the dowel to anchor the fibres in a square path. Since the pattern is random, the direction of the circling depends on the direction of the fibres after the anchor relative to the fibre's direction before the anchor. The script also solved this circling direction. (Figure 5a). At first, the frame path simply circled the dowel from the outside. (Figure 5b). However, during the first-panel fabrication, it was found that some of the dowels were not touching the frame path fibres, especially the middle dowels.

Figure 5. Anchoring winding direction (a) and winding direction of the frame layer - before (b) and after (c) the update.

We found that the fibres pushed the dowel inwards incrementally. This explains why this problem occurred mainly at the upper layers. This problem is reduced by two adjustments for the following panel fabrication: (1) Strengthening the dowel attachment to the mould, and (2) two middle two frame paths. The two middle frame paths weave between the dowels once for each row (Figure 5c). Fibres that touched the dowels from inside of the frame pushed the dowel outward.

The first two-panel fabrication also shows significant collisions between the syringe and the fibres that are already anchored to the dowel on the tip. In the previous winding path algorithm, this collision was already expected to happen because the frame path starts from the tip located on the longer row. Collision was expected to be eliminated by shifting the end of the frame path upward to the next layer (Figure 6 left).

This seemingly simple error has multiple parameters that could affect each other. Testing new fibre syntax would require more time than what is available for a very tight schedule. Thus, some initial fibre panels were wound manually. By winding it manually, a better and simpler solution was found.

To decrease these two types of collisions, the starting point of the frame layer is shifted to the next dowel. Then, the end of the frame layer moved down to the same layer (Figure 6 right). Moving the starting point downward obviously removes the first collision type. It also makes the connecting fibres diagonal. Only the end part of the fibres is in the same layer as the cladding layer. Though it makes the frame layer not closed, the connecting fibres still hold the frame.

Figure 6. Frame layer syntax before and after the amend

Figure 7. Bend fibre panels due to wrong storage position (left) and the amended storage position (right)

3.3. PROCEDURE

After the winding path algorithm was finalized, human-robotic/collaborative winding was preferred. Though faster than collaborative winding, hand winding was exhausting. Transferring task is also difficult. Collaborative winding usually requires two individuals. Robot speed is controlled by one human. One person controls fibre tension and collisions. Sometimes only one person wound, but at a slower speed.

According to Gil Perez et al. (2022), pretension and speed affect product strength. Fibre and adhesive quality also affect product integrity. Several manual control processes were created during fabrication. First, gentle tension was applied to the fibre. Tension is reduced if the dowel bends or when the syringe is near the dowel during frame layer winding. The tension is increased when spanning rows. As the syringe climbs during cladding layer winding, tension is also lowered, and then increased as it descends toward the next dowel. The syringe might alternatively be lifted or the wound fibres briefly lowered to prevent collision.

Fibre panels were wound in 2 weeks. Setting off the adhesive and reinstalling the fibre impede the process. Each panel came out of the mould after one night. Six panels were constructed; hence the maximum number was six. We noticed that finished panels creep during storage. The wrong storage position twists a panel (Figure 7 left). Thus, the remaining panels were stored upright (Figure 7 right).

4. Completion

The Jute Tower assembly started with two steel bar frames that were laid flat on the ground and attached (Figure 8 left). Then, the fibre panels were attached to the steel frames, forming two faces of the panels. Once all faces were completed, they were tilted up and combined, forming the flipped truncated pyramid (Figure 8 right). The connections were either steel wire or smaller jute fibre. The assembling only took a few hours.

Jute Tower stood on display for 3 weeks. This is far longer than the age of the fibre panels. The same sagging could already be found in some panels, especially on the bottom ones. This indicates downward sliding displacement, which affected the bottom panels more than the top ones. To reduce this problem, the top panels were then pulled upward, and more attachment points were added for the top panel. The idea is to anchor each face of the tower on the top, making tensile load the dominant load. After that, there was no significant deformation could be found.

Figure 8. Attaching fibre panels to the steel frame (left) and the completed Jute Tower (right)

5. Disposability

After the exhibition, the disposability of the fibre panels was tested. Even though the fibre panels are naturally biodegradable, the author's experience suggests that weight and volume significantly affect the cost of disposing of materials. Thus, those two variables are discussed in this section.

Fifteen panels, divided into three groups, were handled differently. Each group have one for each level of the tower. The first group was folded directly and put inside trash bags. The second group was submerged in room temperature water first for 5 minutes, individually per panel, before being folded and put inside the trash bags. The third group was also submerged before being folded and put inside the trash bags, but in warm water for 2 minutes instead of room temperature water.

Table 1 shows the results of the disposability test. The first group significantly requires more plastic bags than the other group (Figure 9) but weighs only 0.6 and 0.79 of the second and third groups, respectively. The experience of folding the first group was significantly harder than the other groups. However, compared to other groups, especially the third group, if we included the preparation of heating the water, it was much faster.

Figure 9. The result of the disposability test

Table 1. Disposability test

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Treatment	Dry	Cold water	Warm water
Weight	2.1 kg	3.52	2.65
Volume	2 plastic bag	Half plastic bag	Half plastic bag

It is important to note that the time needed to dissolve the glue on the second and third groups is not relevant due to the timeline and storage issues. The first group was able to be tested around 2 weeks after the dismantling of the tower. Meanwhile, the second and third groups were tested a month later. Other than that, the storage after dismantling is damp. The second and third groups were significantly more pliable than the first group, though they were less pliable compared to themselves after being submerged. Thus, the submerged methods, especially the second group, will require more time if it should be executed immediately after the dismantling. The first group panels could not be compacted and required two plastic bags. If they are disposed of flat, five panels will only require 60x90x5 centimetres cubic. So, if there is a mean to bring them in their broad form, it is simpler to do so.

6. Conclusion

The construction of the Jute Tower is a good exercise for robotic fibre winding. The use of natural fibre and glue shows advantages for collaborative human and robot interaction. The combination of manual fabrication and human interaction also eases the learning curve of robotic fabrication. However, it also imposes imprecision, which are still acceptable for the installation. In the future, more functionalities will be added to the end effector, such as a load cell and a mechanism for automating the tensioning.

Jute Tower has showed the promise of natural fibre impregnated with natural resin as a biodegradable alternative to most Indonesian timber panel materials that use oil-based glue in displays. The tiny experiment reveals that bone glue-impregnated jute panels can be disposed of in various ways.

Different disposal methods affect material volume, weight, and disposal time. Different logistics make scaling that method difficult. Disposing of significant amounts of panels could more time, more cold-water bucket, or energy to heat the water. The easiest approach to dispose of panels is like other board material. It can be stored moist until easier to handle.

Taxoversum façade (“This fiber technology could revolutionize building construction,” 2023) suggests coreless fibre winding for secondary skin. Using natural materials like Jute Tower risks degradation. Combination with oil-base resin will be the next stage in this research to find a durable, low-embodied carbon solution for a secondary skin façade.

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to express gratitude to the ATRIA 2024 team for permitting the use of the exhibition as a platform for experimentation. The Jute Tower installation is

financed by the ATRIA exhibition 2024. This paper is also partly funded by Research, Community Service, and Innovation (PPMI) ITB Program, Bandung Institute of Technology.

References

- Aditra, R. F., & Widyowijatnoko, A. (2016). Combination of mass customisation and conventional construction: A case study of geodesic bamboo dome. CAADRIA 2016, 21st International Conference on Computer-Aided Architectural Design Research in Asia - Living Systems and Micro-Utopias: Towards Continuous Designing, 777–786. Hong Kong: *The Association for Computer-Aided Architectural Design Research in Asia (CAADRIA)*.
- Dahy, H. (2019). Natural Fibre-Reinforced Polymer Composites (NFRP) Fabricated from Lignocellulosic Fibres for Future Sustainable Architectural Applications, Case Studies: Segmented-Shell Construction, Acoustic Panels, and Furniture. *Sensors*, 19(3), 738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19030738>
- Ding, N., Mi, X., & Zhao, L. (2019). Research on Sustainable Development of Event Tourism under Environment-friendly growing path. In IOP Conference Series Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 300, Issue 3, p. 32037). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/300/3/032037>
- Elanchezhian, C., Ramnath, B. V., Ramakrishnan, G., Rajendrakumar, M., Naveenkumar, V., & Kumar, M. S. (2018). Review on mechanical properties of natural fiber composites. In *Materials Today Proceedings* (Vol. 5, Issue 1, p. 1785). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2017.11.276>
- Gil Pérez, M., Guo, Y., & Knippers, J. (2022). Integrative material and structural design methods for natural fibres filament-wound composite structures: The LivMatS pavilion. *Materials and Design*, 217(April). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2022.110624>
- Hamdan, M. H. M., Siregar, J. P., Ahmad, M. R., Asghar, A., Cionita, T., Jaafar, J., & Zalinawati, M. (2020). Characterisation of the woven fabric of jute, ramie and roselle for reinforcement material for polymer composite. In *Materials Today Proceedings* (Vol. 46, p. 1705). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.07.372>
- Lou, Z., Bilitewski, B., Zhu, N., Chai, X., Li, B., Zhao, Y., & Otieno, P. (2015). Greenhouse gas emission and its potential mitigation process from the waste sector in a large-scale exhibition. *Journal of Environmental Sciences (China)*, 31, 44–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jes.2014.12.004>
- Melenbrink, N., Werfel, J., & Menges, A. (2020). On-site autonomous construction robots: Towards unsupervised building. *Automation in Construction*, 119(February). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103312>
- This fiber technology could revolutionize building construction. (2023). *Chemical Engineering*, 130(8), 14. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/trade-journals/this-fiber-technology-could-revolutionize/docview/2848498126/se-2?accountid=31562>
- Widyowijatnoko, A., Irwanuddin, I., & Aditra, R. F. (2019). Reaction as a Synthesis of Reciprocal and Tensegrity Structure. *Nexus Network Journal*, 21(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00004-019-00443-6>
- Widyowijatnoko, Andry, Aditra, R. F., & Cungwin, A. J. (2021). Reaction or Reciprocal Tension as More Efficient Tensegrity. *Earth and Space 2021: Space Exploration, Utilization, Engineering, and Construction in Extreme Environments - Selected Papers from the 17th Biennial International Conference on Engineering, Science, Construction, and Operations in Challenging Environments*, 1351–1362. <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784483374.125>